

OLS Annual report 2024

December 2025

Background

[Open Life Science](#) (OLS) is an organisation dedicated to growing open science ambassadors who create open equitable communities in their own scientific and local domains. OLS is currently funded by the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative via the Silicon Valley Community Foundation ([grant materials](#), [blog announcement](#)), the European Commission via OSCARS ([announcement](#)), and NASA. See our [Funding and Supporters](#) page for more details.

Reports from the previous years

- Annual report for 2020: <https://zenodo.org/records/4778472>
- Annual report for 2021: <https://zenodo.org/records/5907922>
- Annual report for 2022: <https://zenodo.org/records/7305243>

Note on the structure of this report

This report is based on our final report to CZI for the grant "Support for OLS in their education and capacity building efforts through trainings, developing curricula, and maturing their governance structure."

Below, we will cover key grant activities from 2023-09-01 to 2024-12-31 as well as major achievements supported through other funds. The report is structured following OLS's three core pillars of work.

Fig. 1: OLS's three core pillars: Training, Research on open practices, and incubation of the next generation.

Open Science Training

A core part of our CZI grant supports OLS in continuing to deliver [Open Seeds](#), our cohort-based training and mentoring programme for open researchers and leaders worldwide.

Open Seeds OLS-8

We successfully ran our eighth cohort, OLS-8, between September 2023 and Jan 2024.

- 69 mentees from 13 countries developed 32 open research projects in the cohort. Project topics included creating open science handbooks and guides, creating data repositories to share and explore data and creating tools for data analysis in a range of disciplines.
 - 2 of the research projects were Spanish-speaking.
 - We offered 11 microgrants to participants from 5 different countries to facilitate their participation. These typically cover small pieces of hardware (e.g. webcam), and costs for mobile data.
- 38 mentors provided crucial guidance and support along the participants' open journey.
 - We supported 9 mentors with microgrants.
- 12 guest speakers shared their perspectives and experiences with and provided advice to the cohort during cohort calls.
- 15 cohort facilitators, who are graduates from previous cohorts, continue to contribute to delivering cohort calls, from co-hosting calls to correcting cohort call transcripts and sharing recordings on YouTube. Their work is crucial to the accessibility and inclusivity of OLS.

For OLS-8, we specifically partnered with Bioinformatics Hub Kenya Initiative (incubated through OLS-1), SADILAR/Talarify in South Africa, VU Amsterdam and MetaDocencia (Latin America). Beyond offering Open Seeds training for their local communities and supporting local in-person collaboration activities, we worked with core team members at each partner institution from OLS-8's application stage, such that they were actively involved in the intake, review, and selection processes. This resulted in increased participation (>50% applications) from the Global South countries in OLS-8, creating a new collaborative model for the future of Open Seeds.

Open Seeds OLS-9

OLS-8 was the final cohort to be fully funded from our CZI grant; we are pleased to share that OLS-9 was funded primarily by the Digital Research Alliance of Canada, as [training for their EDIA Champions grantees](#). This represents a significant funding model change for OLS, transitioning to a partly service-based funding model rather than a solely grant-funded model.

OLS-9 was the first Open Seeds cohort where we officially ran separate tracks for attendees depending on the programme that sponsored their participation. The cohort

started in September 2024 with final graduations scheduled for January 2025. 18 guest speakers shared their perspectives and experiences with and provided advice to the cohort during cohort calls.

Catalyst

OLS was also part of the CZI-funded [Catalyst Project](#), working with 6 other partners to build open, community-driven cloud computing infrastructure in Latin America and Africa. OLS provided programme management for the collaboration and the project's community partners were invited to participate in OLS-9 to expand their personal open science practice and bring those learnings back to their community.

- 27 mentees have worked on [10 projects](#) in the cohort.
- We supported 18 cohort participants in 7 different countries with microgrants to support their participation in the programme.
- 11 mentors supported the 10 projects on their leadership journey.

DRI EDIA Champions

In partnership with the Digital Research Alliance of Canada, OLS offered its training and mentoring programme to the EDIA champions to support them with reflection on and integration of open science practices into their work.

- [79 champions](#) have participated in the cohort.
- They were supported by 38 mentors. For the first time, OLS combined individual participants with different projects into small groups for mentoring. This allowed participants to learn from other champions with similar interests and approaches as well as an Open Science expert.

Nebula

In addition to OpenSeeds, we also delivered two additional virtual training cohorts for the NASA Open Science 101 training curriculum in 2024. 121 of the OLS cohort participants have earned a NASA certification through our training programs.

The Nebula programme is 6-8 weeks long and covers 10 training sessions as well as graduations and optional social calls. In addition to the cohort sessions, participants have access to one coaching session per cohort in which they can access expertise from our trainers for their concrete projects.

Fig. 2: A mind map of the Nebula curriculum content

Pilot cohort

The pilot cohort for this training ran in March and April 2024.

- 27 people participated in our initial cohort out of which 26 graduated at the end.
- Our participants joined the programme from 15 countries.
- We supported 8 of the participants with microgrants.

Nebula 2

The second cohort for this training ran in October and November 2024.

- 39 people participated in this cohort out of which 24 graduated at the end.
- Our participants joined the programme from 20 countries.
- We supported 13 of the participants with microgrants.

Research on open

OLS has successfully received additional funding to conduct community-based research to inform activities for widening participation in research.

We have successfully completed our [Wellcome Trust Open Research grant](#) to conduct a long-term impact study to specifically report on training and mentoring practices in open science. Overall, the IRB-approved study interviewed ~20 individuals, and found that whilst existing systemic biases and silos exist and are not easily overcome, the training program embedded community-oriented values that participants had not anticipated before joining the program, including now seeing purposeful inclusion as a crucial part of open science, focusing on interpersonally-empowering interactions in research groups and open source projects, and hands-on project management and git technical skills. More is available via preprint:

- Bernaldo, P., Pereyra Irujo, G., Yehudi, Y., van der Walt, A., Iley, B., Míguez, M. P., Ramos, I., Plomp, E., & Sharan, M. (2025). Examining the impact and limitations of Open Science training: a case study of the "Open Seeds" programme. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14930711>

Our exploration of our resident fellowship programme led to our successful Turing Skills Policy Award application, where we received a further GBP 64k (approx USD 80k) for [two additional resident fellowships](#). Our resident fellows investigated and developed policy recommendations for widening the participation of underrepresented groups in open data science in the UK. This research resulted in two recommendation briefs on well-being and team science:

- Sundukova, M., Flavio, A., Chimpén-López, C. A., Iley, B., & Yehudi, Y. (2024). Policy brief: Widening participation in data science: implementing policy for well-being in the workplace. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12759410>
- Sundukova, M., Iley, B., Azevedo, F., Bennett, A., GOKTAS, P., Kiersz, D. A., & Unshur, A. (2024). Policy brief: Equitable & Inclusive Team Science. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12759227>

Open Incubator: Maturing and evolving our incubation of open science initiatives

Fiscal hosting

In July 2024, OLS welcomed its first fiscally sponsored community (FSC). We worked with the [RSE Association of Australia and New Zealand \(RSE-AUNZ\)](#) to support the financial aspects of running their flagship event, the [RSE Asia Australia Unconference 2024 \(RSEAA24\)](#). As part of working with our first fiscally sponsored community, we created a [section on our homepage](#) as well as a [GitHub repository](#) that provides templates for communities that are interested in becoming fiscally sponsored through OLS to work through the prerequisites for becoming an approved FSC.

OLS has started conversations with several other potential fiscally sponsored communities and growing this part of our work into a sustainable business offering will be a major focus in 2025.

Fellowship and mentoring programs

We continue our work on fellowships with the Software Sustainability Institute. OLS is a key partner in the [SSI's next funding phase \(2024-2028\)](#), supporting the SSI in developing the mentorship aspect of their Fellowship programme. With several members of the OLS team being SSI Fellows, we will be actively mentoring the next generation of leaders in research software.

Our Resident Fellowship program allowed us to experiment with different models of community interaction and support. We trialled alternative value-exchange methods

with "Senior Resident Fellows" who needed institutional affiliation but did not need direct supervision or salary to carry out their work. This included work with Rowland Mosbergen of [Practical Diversity and Inclusion](#) to launch RSE-oriented leadership course material, and Gracielle Higino for supporting OLS-g.

Building operational capacity

One of our core areas of focus is to keep strengthening our operational effectiveness - to build foundational frameworks and capacity to be able to plan for long-term sustainability. Some of the activities and achievements towards this goal are highlighted below:

- Establishing a resilient finance team: In early 2023, Patricia Herterich joined our core team as a part-time Fellowship and Finance Manager to support Emmy Tsang. From April 2024, she acted as Chief of Staff, leading OLS's finance work to replace Emmy Tsang. Emmy Tsang took leave in April 2024 and stepped down as Director of Finance and Operations in August 2024. In June 2024, Bethan Iley (a Resident Fellow on the Turing Skills Policy Award project) joined the core team as Finance Manager to provide additional finance support. Throughout 2024, the finance team has continued to improve processes to administer microgrants and compensate mentors, facilitators and expert guest speakers for our own training as well as our fiscally sponsored community. The team also worked on documentation of finance processes and budgeting as well as grant reporting.
- Continuing from our rebranding, we created a dedicated web team to work on promoting our activities. Director of Learning and Technology Bérénice Batut worked with our designer Jilaga Nneoma and developer Deborah Udoh on updating the data and information architecture to create our new website at our new domain we-are-ols.org. Our knowledge management system is documented at https://we-are-ols.org/knowledge_management.html
 - Jilaga worked on icons representing our core three pillars and our new website now is structured along the team's core area offerings.

OLS is a **not-for profit** organisation dedicated to **capacity building** and **diversifying leadership** in research worldwide. We imagine a future where research is accessible, inclusive, and equitable for everyone.

Our three pillars

<p>Open Incubator</p> <p>The greenhouse: Hands-on support to empower the next generation of open leaders in research.</p>		
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Fig. 3: Screenshot of the redesigned OLS main webpage

- Governance committee: We kept working with our [governance committee](#) throughout 2024. Having spent the first six months with the committee reviewing and creating key documentation for their work, we made our governance process available for reuse in a [GitHub repository](#).

We held monthly meetings with the governance committee throughout 2024 to ensure we make the most of their expertise to support the organization's sustainability and transparency. The report from our committee covering discussions and reflections from July through December 2024 is available at <https://we-are-ols.org/posts/2025/05/07/ols-governance-report/>.

Key outputs and project recognition

Identifier (URL or DOI)	Title
https://zenodo.org/communities/openlifesci	OLS-6 and 7 graduation presentations (also available on YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/@OpenLifeSci/videos)
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zJzkGvfDspI&list=PL1CvC6Ez54KCuzVZwIkHjICoSrwXz5Ucx	OLS-8 graduations

https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10884382	Using the OLS training programme as a launch pad for NASA TOPS Open Science 101 cohorts (Talk by Irene Ramos and Yo Yehudi at the Year of Open Science (YOS) conference)
https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1011797	Ten simple rules for pushing boundaries of inclusion at academic events (Paper resulting from a project in OLS-7; OLS team members Malvika Sharan and Patricia Herterich are co-authors)
https://github.com/open-life-science/ols-governance/tree/main/docs	Repository with governance documentation for OLS for wider reuse
https://zenodo.org/badge/DOI/10.5281/zenodo.14931072.svg	Ecological Society of America talk: "Does diversifying lead to decolonizing science?" Talk by Yo Yehudi

OLS cohort members and fellows share their project reports on Zenodo, where additional outputs can be found: <https://www.zenodo.eu/communities/openlifesci/>.

Additional recognition for the open source project(s) and/or key personnel

- OLS was shortlisted for the [Einstein Foundation Award in 2023](#) and again in 2024 for promoting quality in research.
- Several OLS community members were selected as [Software Sustainability Institute \(SSI\) Fellows 2024](#): OLS team member Deborah Udoh, Esther Plomp (OLS mentor and governance committee member), Arielle Bennet (OLS mentor), Jyoti Bhogal (OLS-5 mentee), and Nicky Nicolson (OLS-6 mentee).